

PLA LIGHTWEIGHT PACKAGING IN THE POST- CONSUMER RECYCLING STREAM

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Abstract: Due to the increasing use of bio-based plastics in the market, also materials, which are partly chemically novel, are entering the established disposal routes for plastic waste. The majority of these chemically novel plastics lightweight packaging (LWP) in the German post-consumer waste stream is Polylactic acid (PLA) and the potentials and challenges of these materials must be determined. The results presented show the conditions under which common industrial sorting facilities can sort out PLA lightweight packaging waste, the challenges that arise when processing the post-consumer material and the extent to which they can be mechanically recycled.

Keywords: plastic waste, lightweight packaging, NIR separation, mechanical recycling

1 INTRODUCTION

In Germany, a functioning recycling system for lightweight packaging (LWP) made of plastics has been in operation for three decades through the Duales System Deutschland. This system is set up for the known quantitative main fractions of polyolefins (PP and PE), polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and polystyrene (PS), of which a certain amount can be separated and regenerated. The latest material flow diagram for Germany (Conversio, 2020) reports a total plastic waste volume of 6.28 megatonnes (Mt), of which approx. 0.93 Mt is post-industrial and 5.35 Mt is post-consumer waste. LWP products are the

main component with 59% or 3.16 Mt. Figure 1 provides the extracted information and data of the Conversio report in relation to the total post-consumer waste in Germany in 2019 and its quantitative path through the recycling system.

Figure 1: Post-consumer waste stream in Germany with quantities from 2019 (Conversio, 2020)

More than 60 % is sent for energy recovery and almost 14 % is exported abroad. The remaining 25% of the waste stream is almost completely recycled mechanically. Of the 5.35 Mt of post-consumer waste, 19.2 % or around 1 Mt is subsequently put back on the market as recyclates.

Currently, there are no valid figures for the share of bioplastics in the post-consumer waste stream in Germany. A non-representative study (Hädrich et al., 2014) carried out at one German sorting facility in 2014 showed a value of approximately 1‰ bioplastics in the LWP stream, consisting mainly of polylactic acid (PLA) and thermoplastic starch (and its blends). The only valid data available are the global production capacities of bioplastics of the nova-Institute (European Bioplastics, 2020), which amount to 2.11 Mt for the year 2020, of which 47% are accounted for by the area of flexible and rigid packaging and thus indicate approx. 1.0 Mt of bioplastics worldwide in the market. Considering this amount in relation to the reported 40.4 Mt total volume of flexible and rigid packaging worldwide (Smithers Report, 2020), the market share of bioplastics is 2.5 % in this sector.

The BMEL¹-funded joint project "Sustainable recycling strategies for products and waste from bio-based plastics" was initiated to contribute to closing these knowledge gaps and to identifying efficient recycling options for bioplastics in relation to the quantity in the established recycling system. The results presented in the following for PLA as the most widespread bioplastic in terms of quantity were gathered by KNOTEN WEIMAR – International Transfer Centre Environmental Technology GmbH and the Department of Lightweight Structures and Polymer Technology at Chemnitz University of Technology the project collaborates in sub-project 1² "BioRec – Bio-based plastics in the post-consumer recycling stream".

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Recovery of PLA LWP from the post-consumer waste stream

In order to test the detectability of PLA waste in industrial sorting practice, tests were carried out on sorting plants. The plants were cleaned in advance for the sorting experiments, but all other parameters corresponded to standard operation (e.g. throughput 10 t per h). Due to the low proportion of PLA light packaging in the waste stream, approx. 2 t of the post-consumer waste on site was charged with 160 kg PLA LWP and mixed (cf. Figure 2).

Figure 2: PLA LWP samples (left hand side), charged post-consumer waste (center) and mixing (right hand side)

Two experiments carried out on the same sorting plant at B&R Bioverwertung und Recycling GmbH close to Erfurt are discussed in more detail. Sorting test 1 is with sorting operation on the standard fractions in order to see which fraction the PLA waste is allocated to, without adaptation of the NIR scanners. Sorting trial 2 is after plant optimisation for PLA as a separate recyclable

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fraction in order to obtain the potentially possible sorting rate for PLA. The test set-ups and results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Overview sorting test set up and results

	Sorting test 1	Sorting test 2
Waste input (post-consumer/PLA)	1.98 t / 0.16 t	1.92 t / 0.16 t
Plant throughput	10 tons per hour	10 tons per hour
Sorting fraction/s	PE/PP PET PVC	PLA
PLA output in fractions	in PE/PP: 4.3 kg / 2.7% in PET: 0.8 kg / 0.5% in PVC: 14.3 kg / 8.9%	88 kg / 55%

In preparation for the above mentioned and other sorting tests on PLA, an NIR spectra database of common PLA LWPs was created. This database was also used in sorting test 2 to modify the plant NIR scanners (UniSort P2000). A total of nine different PLA products (post consumer) were scanned multiple times and an average spectrum was determined. Figure 3 outlines the procedure using a drinking cup (consisting of neat PLA) and an organic-waste bag, which is made of a PLA compound (with approx. 50% PLA content). The PLA compound was selected because it is frequently used also in many LWP applications.

Figure 3: NIR spectra of post-consumer beverage cup (left hand side) and organic waste bag (right hand side). Single spectra (red) and average spectrum (black)

2. 2 Processing test of post consumer PLA

In the second part of the project, the processing of post-consumer PLA LWP was investigated. The post-consumer PLA input material was obtained from a larger sorting test than described in 2.1. The material obtained was prepared (shredded, wind-sifted and washed) in the same way as usual post-consumer material before processing. A grade purity of 94.5% was determined by

selectively dissolving out the PLA by a partner in the joint-project. The 5.5% contamination was predominantly label residue (paper) stuck together with PLA flakes, which is a major challenge for processing. The processing test was carried out at SysPlast GmbH on a twin-screw extruder equipped with rotary filter technology at a throughput of 300 kg/h. The detailed test configuration is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Processing test configuration for processing post-consumer PLA cuttings with 5.5% contamination

As a result, 226 kg of deep green PLA regranulate (cf. Figure 5) were obtained. The filter discharge was measured at 6 kg and there was a further 5 kg in the discharge screw and on the melt filter.

Figure 5: Obtained PLA regranulate (a), filter discharge (b), discharge screw (c) and melt filter (d)

The obtained PLA regranulate was injected to test specimens and the mechanical properties were characterised and compared with a commercially available post-industrial PLA and virgin material PLA2003D. The results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Preparation of compostability test

The post-consumer recyclate was processed after adequate pre-drying, but without any processing or modifying additives. Therefore, the results for the mechanical properties can easily be optimised at this point.

3 CONCLUSION

The results show that PLA can be sorted out of the post-consumer LWP waste stream by marginal adjustments of the plant sorting technology. The gained result of 55% recovery rate mentioned in 2.1. was also lowered by the test samples because almost all of the PLA camping forks (cf. Figure 2) were removed from the waste stream by fine sieve section before the NIR scanner line. In sorting test 1 (without adaption) a frequently mentioned and reported contamination of the PET stream was observed at 0.5%. However, almost 9% of the PLA LWP was allocated to the PVC stream. Figure 7 shows the PVC spectrum used at the plant together with two PLA average spectra (cf Figure 3).

Figure 7: PVC spectrum (black) of the plant NIR and average spectra of waste bag (green) and beverage cup (blue) from the created PLA database

As a possible explanation, the very sensitive sorting of PVC (flattened spectrum) from the waste stream can be mentioned, as it is not permitted to enter common waste incineration plants due to decomposing by-products during incineration.

The presented processing experiment served as the data basis for the life cycle assessment, which was prepared in another sub-project of the joint-project (Maga, 2019). The gained mechanical properties (cf. Figure 6) show that the reduction of tensile strength by 30% should be the primary target for optimisation by additives (e.g. chain extenders or stabilisers) in achieving a property profile that is competitive with the commercially available PLA post-industrial material.

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